

PECULIARITIES OF NOUNS IN FRENCH LANGUAGE

Nilufar Juraeva

Assistant professor, PhD
French Philology Department
Bukhara State University
n.s.juraeva@buxdu.uz

Shodmonova Barchinoy

Student of Bukhara State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14937501>

Annotation: A noun is an independent part of speech that denotes an object, person or phenomenon and answers the questions “who?” “what?” or “where?”. A noun is an important word class in any language, including French. This article discusses the specific features of nouns in French.

Keywords: noun, animate and inanimate objects, proper noun, common noun, definite noun, abstract noun, countable nouns, uncountable noun, simple noun, complex noun, grammatical category, number category, singular, plural, masculine, feminine.

Introduction. A word group that denotes the names of animate and inanimate objects, actions, qualities, abstract concepts is called a noun. A noun is a label for places, things, and concepts. In French language nouns may be categorised:

- common or proper
- counting or mass
- singular (sg.) or plural (pl.),
- masculine (m.) or feminine (f.).

It is important to recognise the gender and the number of a noun. These properties affect the form of the determiner, pronouns, and adjectival/participial agreement. Thus, most of time French nouns are preceded by a determiner. For example: C’est la vie! That’s life! The construction: *C’est vie is not possible in French. The most common determiners are articles, appearing before the noun, (e.g., la vie) and indicate definiteness. La introduces a feminine and singular noun. French articles change form to agree in gender and number with the noun. There is also a contracted form used before words starting with a vowel and most words beginning with “h”.

	Singular	plural	Singular	plural
Masculine	Le		Les	
Feminine	La		Les	
Before vowel or h	L’		Les	

Some examples of noun with their corresponding definite article

Le garçon/les garçons	the boy(s)
la fille/les filles	the girl(s)
L'appartement/les appartements	the flat(s)
L'université/les universités	the universitie(s)

Main part. In this article, we will discuss the peculiarities of the nouns, such as gender and number categories in the French language.

Nouns in French can be divided into the following types:

1. Names of animate and inanimate objects: fille, chien, livre, table;
2. Proper nouns: Jacques, Paul, Paris, Seine, Tashkent and common nouns: garçon, ville, rivière, fenêtre;
3. Definite nouns: crayon, porte, clé, table and abstract nouns: patience, amour, sourire, peur, amitié;
4. Nouns denoting a person and an object: enfant, feuille, papier and collective nouns: foule, groupe, feuillage;
5. Countable nouns: cahier, pomme, allumettes and uncountable nouns. Uncountable nouns are, in turn, divided into nouns denoting objects: eau, sucre, farine, viande and abstract nouns: force, patience, musique.
6. Simple nouns: plume, garde, stylo, porte and complex nouns: porte-plume, avant-garde.

Gender. Every French noun has a gender, either masculine (m) or feminine (f). All people, places or things are either masculine or feminine and it is easier to learn the French noun with its gender. It is important to know a noun's gender because every time we use an adjective with a noun, we might need to change its spelling if the noun is feminine or plural. If we don't know the gender of a word, we can look it up in a dictionary or online. There are some clues which will help to remember the gender of a noun.

Masculine gender. There are few general patterns and rules that help to identify the gender and number of French nouns. Common endings:

- A) Nouns ending in -é, -er, -ier → Le café (the coffee), l'atelier (the studio), le dîner (the lunch)...
- B) Nouns ending in -ent → document (the document), le moment (the moment), L'appartement (the apartment)
- C) Nouns ending in -isme → Le socialisme (the socialism), le capitalisme (the capitalism), le nihilisme (the nihilism)...

D) Nouns ending in -eau, -o, -eu → Le cerveau (the brain), le vélo (the bicycle), le jeu (the game) ...

E) Most compound nouns → Le tire-bouchon (the corkscrew), le pique-nique (the picnic), le passe-temps (the pastime) ...

In French language all weekdays, seasons and languages are masculine.

Masculine number. The plural form of nouns. To form the regular plural, add -s to the end of the noun:

L'étudiant/Les étudiants the student(s)

Irregular nouns and compound nouns have different rules. When a noun ends in -s, -x or -z, there is no difference between the singular and plural forms:

Le bras/Les bras the arm(s)

Le gaz/Les gaz the gaz/gases

Le prix/Les prix the price(s)

Irregular patterns:

Ending	Singular	Plural	Translation
-ail	Le travail	Les travaux	Work, job(s)
-al	Le journal	Les journaux	Newspaper(s)
-eau	Le cadeau	Les cadeaux	Present(s)
-eu	Le jeu Les jeux game(s)	Le jeu Les jeux game(s)	Le jeu Les jeux game(s)
-ou	Le bijou	Les bijoux	Jewel(s)

Feminine gender. Common endings:

A) Nouns ending in -ure or -ue → La culture (the culture), la voiture (the car), la rue (the street), l'aventure (the adventure)...

B) Nouns ending in -tion or -(s)sion → La passion (the passion), la dissertation (the essay), l'émotion (the emotion), la nation (the nation)...

C) Nouns ending in -ée → La matinée (morning), la journée (day), la soirée (evening), l'idée (idea)...

D) Most common nouns ending in -té → La clarté (clarity), la médiocrité (mediocrity), la santé (health), la pauvreté (poverty) ...

E) Most nouns ending in -ie → La pluie (rain), la pâtisserie (pastry shop), la pharmacie (pharmacy), l'académie (academy) ...

F) Nouns ending in -ance → La méfiance (distrust), l’arrogance (arrogance), la chance (chance), la vengeance (revenge)...

G) Most nouns ending in -ence → La préférence (preference), l’absence (absence), la patience (patience), la conférence (conference)...

H) Most nouns ending in -eur → La peur (fear), la couleur (colour), la grandeur (size), l’erreur (mistake) etc...

I) Most nouns ending in a double consonant followed by -e → La ville (the city), la couronne (the crown), la famille (the family), l’adresse (address)...

In general, sciences are feminine except Le droit (law):

In French	Translation
L’anthropologie	Anthropology
La biologie	Biology
La chimie	Chemistry
La géographie	Geography
La linguistique	Linguistics
La médecine	Medecine
La physique	Physics
La politique	Politics
...	...

In all these cases, the plural is formed by adding -s to the noun:

L’étudiante → les étudiantes

La directrice → les directrices

La danseuse → les danseuses

Conclusion. Nouns play an important role in expressing the name of the subject. As it is known, the concept of gender exists in the French language. In French, nouns are divided into two: le masculin and le féminin. In dictionaries, they are abbreviated as m and f. In French, there are a number of nouns that can belong to both genders, but they are fundamentally different from each other in meaning. A deep study of the specific grammatical and semantic aspects of nouns will help to better understand their role and significance in the language system.

References:

1. Н. А. Баскаков, Каракалпакский язык, II часть, 1952. – Б. 301.
2. A.E.Mamatov, M.M.Mirxoliqov, A.S.Asqarov. Fransuz tilining amaliy grammatikasi. – T.: “Fan texnologiya”, 2015. – B.34
3. Ona tili (morfologiya): o’quv qo’llanma / U. Amonov. – Buxoro: “Sadridin Salim Buxoriy” Durдона, 2021. – B. 216.

4. Nazarov K., Sayfullayeva R., Ubaydullayeva M. O'zbek tili (ixtisoslik grammatikasi). –Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1993. – B.30.
5. Juraeva N. Pragmatic features of dysphemisms in French //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 196-201.
6. Juraeva N., Beshimova D. The phenomena of taboo and euphemism in french linguistics //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 9. – №. 7. – С. 67-71.
7. Juraeva N., Farangiz K. Specific features of adjectives in French and Uzbek languages //Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. – 2025. – Т. 12. – №. 01. – С. 588-591.

